

Morón in perspective: the end of Cuban exceptionalism

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The power that governs through fear has the advantage of maintaining its hold for long periods; the huge disadvantage is that, when fear weakens, nothing stops its fall. That is the point that we are at today in Cuba. The protests in Morón¹ can only be understood if we analyse the course of the last few decades diachronically. This article attempts to provide such a perspective.

By arguing so much about the supposed exceptionalism of the Cuban historical process and having decreed that socialism was irreversible, the government ideologists made the mistake of believing it. That way, they turned their backs on the historical experience without considering the consequences that this would entail. Despite repeating like a mantra that this was a revolution “of the humbles, by the humbles and for the humbles,” they thought that the humble would not dare to remember it, that they would maintain the silence for which they had been carefully conditioned.

Achieving such a stance of civic withdrawal required systematic cultural practices across the family, schools, media, and political discourse. Obedience was the cornerstone of achieving a neutralised civil society and a demobilised citizenry; hence, most dissenting attitudes and political conflicts in Cuba are categorised as “disobedience”.

For people to be obedient, they must fear change. A future outside the boundaries drawn by the State through its control mechanisms, whether symbolic or overtly repressive, must seem insecure to them. However, when the conditions of existence reach the point of no longer guaranteeing daily life and dignity, the instinct for survival, common to all species, emerges; the fear of change disappears, and as a result, the entire political structure trembles.

The bonfire in front of the Morón municipal party’s headquarters symbolizes that weakened structure: still with power —the power of weapons— but no longer under control, because control requires hegemony and cunning.

I

The social consensus that guaranteed obedience amongst the majority of the people ended in Cuba when the State transferred to individuals and families the responsibilities it had long presented as its “social achievements”; when the populist authoritarian State became an anti-popular authoritarian State. And that happened with Raúl Castro’s rise to power.

Spending was cut immediately, and “improper gratuities” were eliminated. The measures affected the poorest people and families: 24,000 workers’ canteens were closed; the retirement age was raised by 5 years; the minimum working age was lowered to 15; and the right to a free lunch was suspended for students who were not living in university residence halls, disproportionately impacting poor families.

Between 2006 and 2018, the budget allocated to social assistance contracted from 2.2% to 0.3%, while the number of beneficiaries as a proportion of the population decreased from 5.3% to 1.6%. The 2011

¹ Protest that occurred on Friday night, 13th March 2026, at the Municipal Cuban Communist Party’s headquarters in Morón (Municipality of the central Cuban province Ciego de Ávila). See a report here: <https://eltoque.com/en/moron-protests-demonstrators-burn-symbols-outside-communist-party-headquarters-and-demand-freedom>.

budget law revealed the pronounced deterioration of social assistance indicators between 2009 and 2010. The number of beneficiaries fell by 61% compared to 2005, and as a percentage of the total population, the number dropped from 5.3% to 2.1%. In 2010 alone, 237 million pesos² were cut due to “beneficiary cleansing”. One of the guidelines approved in 2011 at the Sixth Congress of the Communist Party of Cuba (PCC in Castilian Spanish) prohibited social assistance for individuals with families capable of supporting them.

The situation was exacerbated by the sustained decline in investments in sectors with direct social impact, such as health and education, which decreased in direct proportion to the increase in investments in the tourism and real estate sectors. This spending cut was also explained by the payment of the external debt, renegotiated during Raúl Castro's term.

During those years, even with measures that increased the cost of living, wages were not generally increased, only in certain sectors such as health, education, and priority businesses. The elderly and retirees could barely make ends meet, given the pension system's inability to keep pace with the sustained increase in the cost of living. At that time, economist Mauricio de Miranda considered pensions “insufficient and unfair,” condemning many to poverty.

The technocratic military class, which increasingly amassed economic benefits for itself and its cronies, not content with impoverishing those below, also demonstrated its contempt for them. In July 2013, Raúl Castro dedicated almost half of his address to parliament to showing that “the nobility of the Revolution has been abused, the decision not to resort to the force of law, however justified it may have been,” [and lamented](#) that “We have painfully witnessed, throughout the more than twenty years of the Special Period³, the growing deterioration of moral and civic values, such as honesty, decency, shame, decorum, integrity, and sensitivity to the problems of others.” Indeed, poverty and social and regional inequalities had steadily increased in Cuba since the Special Period, but this was not mentioned in his speech.

When Raúl Castro took over the leadership of the country, Cuba ranked 51st in the world based on the Human Development Index; when he left office, we were in 73rd place. His successor, Miguel Díaz-Canel, continued his social policies. Currently, we are in 97th place. A drop of 46 places.

On January 1st, 2021, when the “Ordering Task” began⁴, Cuban society was already impoverished and plagued by enormous social inequalities. Then the debacle occurred. Hyperinflation quickly decimated wages; the ration book⁵, which had withstood the harsh 1990s, became a collection of blank pages; and businesses began to dollarize their prices. Too many people fell into precarious situations and began to experience hunger, and nothing politicizes people more than hunger, need, and hopelessness. Six months later, the July 11 social uprising⁶ took place.

II

In the following years, with utter irresponsibility, the regime's propaganda machine celebrated as a victory the fact that no further protests erupted on that July date. Of course, in addition to celebrating,

² The official currency in Cuba is Cuban Pesos.

³ Special Period is the term used in Cuba to name the period of extreme hardship after the Soviet Union and the European Socialist Bloc collapsed in the early 1990s.

⁴ This was a package of economic and financial reforms imposed by the government, focusing on four areas: monetary and exchange rate unification, the phase-out of subsidies, and income reform.

⁵ A record-keeping notebook for each household to give you access to and accountability for the government-subsidised products.

⁶ Likely the biggest post-1959 social uprising in Cuba: <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2021/7/11/thousands-join-rare-anti-government-protests-in-cuba>; <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/07/11/cuba-crackdown-protests-creates-rights-crisis>

they took precautions: surveillance of dissidents, threats, summonses, and police cars stationed outside the homes of certain inconvenient individuals.

In the 2022 article “[The Pyrrhic Victory of 11-J](#)”, I assessed the stubbornness in that optimism: “Such an attitude ignores that 11-J, 2021, occurred due to a set of circumstances, not only present today, but much more amplified. Those who believe that by preventing it on a fixed date, they eliminated the conditions for similar actions are either naive or arrogant, and in both cases, they are inept politicians.”

Following the events of July 11, the State fortified itself to discourage any action against it: the 9151 Council of Ministers Agreement; a Communications Law that functions like George Orwell's “Big Brother”; a much stricter Penal Code; harsh prison sentences for protesters; and constant threats and coercion against any citizen by the political police. To prevent any dissent, none of the constitutional laws that would allow citizens to challenge the State—the right to demonstrate, and the Constitutional Court—were enacted.

However, to the same extent that repression by the State has become normalised, so too have social protest and civil disobedience. It is a process of reciprocal adaptation, reinforced in both cases, the more it is practiced. Even though they have not reached the magnitude of July 11, social protests and dissent have continued to grow in Cuba. They have become more argumentative and have garnered massive support, and something very interesting is that they are increasingly involving more young people.

III

Below, I analyse certain aspects that can be inferred from the events of recent weeks:

- When Donald Trump’s administration decided to adopt a more forceful policy against the Cuban government, the contradictions that had fuelled citizen protests on the island were already ripe. The Cuban model is imploding due to a long-standing systemic crisis of a civilizational character. People are starving in a country full of unlaboured fertile land and stores in dollars where they can find products from the United States, the country that “blocks” us.
- What happened at the Morón Communist Party headquarters is evidence of how much accumulated anger, despair, the fact of being ignored, cruel treatment, humiliation, abandonment, poverty, and the brutal deterioration of living conditions can influence human behaviour.
- People are now demanding freedom before food, a significant change that reflects growing political awareness. And also political maturity, as we saw in the young man who refused to burn the Cuban flag because “that's ours, the flag of our freedom.” It was not senseless vandalism, as the official media have tried to portray it; there was much more to it.
- Having prevented the existence of a structured opposition in Cuba, by persecuting and forcing to emigrate in many cases people who could exercise some leadership, the authorities have a harder time: social uprisings are spontaneous, without coordinating leaders, and can be violent. And the entire responsibility for this lies with the police state: if the door to dialogue is closed, it is opened to violence.
- The constant repression of peaceful protests by the authorities has generated its nemesis: violent protest. The exaggerated, exemplary sentences handed down to people who only shouted slogans, covered themselves with a flag, wrote a sign, or went out to protest without any violence, have convinced many that, if they are going to prison for long periods anyway, it does not matter if force is used. When the balance of judgment is lost, the balance of action is also lost.

- But there is something that is not insignificant: Cuba has the second-highest prison population per capita in the world. It is so enormous that it is costly for a State already in economic collapse. There are reports of malnutrition and lack of medical attention for inmates. In the last three years, at least 122 people have died in State custody. In the province of Ciego de Ávila, where the city of Morón is located, a protest took place a few weeks ago at the Canaleta prison because the prisoners were going hungry.

If the protests escalate and become massive, it will be difficult for the prison system to absorb a critical mass of new political prisoners without consequences: new families joining the activism; complaints in international forums; and, worst of all, the elimination of the immediate possibility of a general amnesty, a fundamental issue in any dialogue process.

The Cuban State maintained control as long as it managed to govern without resorting to blatant repression. The paradox is that a State that fails to demonstrate control over its citizens is a weak negotiator. And the power group that governs Cuba has just announced that it is in dialogue with the U.S. government.

This makes the situation potentially dangerous, as they may try to demonstrate control through a brutal escalation of violence. Police patrols have already been seen driving in convoys through the streets of Havana. Yesterday⁷, eight trucks full of soldiers were seen leaving a military unit in the province of Artemisa.

If the Cuban government were to opt for bloody repression of likely mass protests, it would not only damage its position in the dialogue with the North Americans (the only dialogue it has ever desired), but it would also be exposed to international public opinion and could unleash an unstoppable wave of citizen protest.

Nothing exceptional happens in Cuba. In any era and context where a government has impoverished the people, ignored the popular will, and repressed them with violence, social protest has been the response. This is an eminently political crisis. They thought we were invisible; we are not. For them, we do not exist, but we are here.

Cuba x Cuba (CXC) is a virtual meeting space that, like a civic think tank, draws on specific and collective knowledge to generate analyses and proposals in order to help improve the Cuban nation, which is much more than the physical space of the country. (Translated from [the think tank's website](#))

⁷ As this article was released on Monday 16th of March, the author refers to Sunday 15th of March 2026.